

Two nets, 561 m² each with 36-cm² mesh, were supported 2.5 m above ground level by bamboo stakes at Masapang, Victoria, Philippines. The nets were positioned in such a way that they completely covered the plants within each plot.

Treatments involved the Binato, Utri Rajapan, and Bigas Pula varieties with four replications. Similar varieties without a net served as the control. Plots were assessed before and after the nets were set up to determine the extent of bird damage. Beginning 94 d after

transplanting nets were kept in place for 9 d over Utri Rajapan and Binato, and 17 d over Bigas Pula.

Bird damage was assessed by counting the total number of damaged and undamaged panicles from 10 randomly selected hills per plot (21 m²). In addition to the random samples, three to four hills from the borders of each plot were sampled because we observed that birds preferentially attack the border plants.

Bigas Pula and Utri Rajapan plots without a net sustained significantly

more bird damage, compared to those with a net. However, no difference was found for Binato because bird damage occurred before the net was installed. It is also likely that this variety sustained more damage because it was located at the outermost portion of the experimental field making it more susceptible to bird attack.

Although this is a preliminary test, our results show that nets may be a satisfactory solution to the problem of bird damage, especially in plots where maximum protection is needed. *ℳ*

Soil and Crop Management

Effects of pyrite used as farmer on normal soils

D. M. Maurya and M. P. Yadav, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology, Narendra Nagar, P. O. Kumarganj, Faizabad 224001 (U.P.), India

Pyrite is generally used to normalize saline-alkali soils.

During 1980-81, some farmers who casually applied pyrite as a topdressing obtained surprisingly good results. They contacted us to verify the relevance of pyrite application and the appropriate application rates. A trial under normal soil achieved positive results and a detailed experiment was undertaken.

Variety Sarjoo 52 was grown in a split-plot design with three replications. Soil texture was silty loam with 7.6 pH, 0.82% organic matter, 17.6 kg available P, and CEC 24.8 meq 100 g of soil. Chemical composition of the pyrite used was 22.3% S, 20.5% Fe, 0.58% MgO, 0.13% CaO, 6.8% Al, 36.8% Si, 2.72% C, 200 ppm Zn, 500 ppm CuO, and 122 ppm Mn.

Four levels of ground pyrite — 200 kg, 400 kg, and 600 kg, and no pyrite (control) were tested at 3 fertility levels — 60-13.6-24, 80-18-32, and 120-27.248 kg NPK/ha. All P and K and half N were applied basally; the remaining N was applied in two equal installments at tillering and panicle initiation.

Table 1. Effect of pyrite levels at different fertility levels on grain yield of rice. Faizabad, U. P., India.

Fertility level (kg NPK/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at pyrite level of				Mean yield (t/ha)
	0	200 kg	400 kg	600 kg	
Low (60-13.6-24)	2.7	2.7	2.9	3.3	2.9
Medium (80-18.0-32)	2.9	3.0	3.3	3.6	3.2
High (120-27.2-48)	3.5	3.8	3.9	3.9	3.8
Mean	3.0	3.2 (1.51)	3.4 (3.32)	3.6 (5.73)	
Fertility combination CD at 5%	0.1		pyrite 0.2	Interaction ns	

Table 2. Grain yield and ancillary characters as affected by pyrite topdressing at different fertility levels. Faizabad, U. P., India, 1984-85.

Treatments	Panicles/ linear m	Wt/panicle (g)	Grains/ panicle	1000- grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Fertility levels (kg NPK/ha)					
Low (60-13.6-24)	48	2.89	114	22.3	2.9
Medium (80-18-32)	50	2.95	118	22.4	3.2
High (120-27.2-48)	53	2.89	124	22.5	3.8
CD at 5%	—	—	5	—	1.4
Pyrite doses (kg/ha)					
0	47	2.80	115	22.4	3.0
200	49	2.85	117	22.4	3.2
400	51	2.91	119	22.3	3.4
600	55	3.08	121	22.4	3.6
CD at 5%	—	0.14	—	—	1.7

The pyrite was topdressed 20 d after transplanting. The crop was irrigated as needed.

Grain yields increased at all application levels up to 600 kg/ha (Table 1). Response was highest at medium fertility.

The yield increase was due to

increased panicle weight (Table 2). Although the data did not show significant increases in panicle numbers per linear m or grain numbers per panicle, both characters increased with pyrite applications.

That pyrite is rich in S, Fe, and Si and has traces of Zn and Mn might be

responsible for the yield increase. At this stage, the response to different levels of pyrite appears to be due to widespread deficiencies of many elements in Uttar Pradesh soil. *ℒ*

Effect of nitrogen source, rate, and placement method on growth and yield

G.R. Singh and T.A. Singh, Soil Science Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, U.P. India

The efficiency of urea, urea supergranules (USG), and NPK (12-32-16) rates and placement methods in flooded lowland transplanted rice was studied in 1984 kharif. The design used three N rates and placement methods in a randomized block design with three replications.

Twenty-three-day-old Jaya rice seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing. The soil (Beni silty clay loam) had pH 7.2, 1.51% organic C, CEC 23.91 meq/ 100 g of soil, and percolation rate of 15.3 mm/d. Treatments are described in the table.

All plots except NPK treatments received 28 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 26 kg K/ha as muriate of potash.

Effect of source, rate, and placement of N on yield attributes of rice.

Treatment ^a		Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/m ²	Gram yield (t/ha)
Rate (kg N/ha)	Source and application			
0	(control)	75.3	157	2.9
60	Urea, 3 splits	78.0	199	4.1
90	Urea, 3 splits	81.9	218	5.1
120	Urea, 3 splits	84.2	239	5.4
60	USG B&I at transplanting	76.8	207	4.0
90	USG B&I at transplanting	79.6	220	4.8
120	USG B&I at transplanting	84.0	290	5.2
60	USG deep placed 11 DT	84.4	243	4.8
90	USG deep placed 11 DT	88.2	253	5.3
120	USG deep placed 11 DT	89.2	303	5.4
60	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	77.9	191	4.0
90	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	81.5	209	4.9
120	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	84.4	214	5.3
120	24 kg N/ha at transplanting + 96 kg N/ha as urea in 2 equal splits at tillering & panicle initiation	90.8	296	5.8
120	24 kg N/ha at transplanting + 96 kg N/ha as USG deep placed 11 DT	89.3	308	5.1
CD (0.05)		2.6	14	0.2

^a B&I = broadcast and incorporated. Deep placed USG is put in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows at 8-10 cm depth. DT = days after transplanting.

At 60 kg N/ha, yields from deep placed USG were significantly superior to those from 3 splits of urea, USG broadcast and incorporated (B&I) at transplanting, and 2/3 N as USG B&I

at transplanting, and 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation. Above 60 kg N/ha, response to deep placed USG was less than the response to N applied by other methods. *ℒ*

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Energy use in rice-based farming system in India

A. S. Saini, Regional Research Station, Dhaulakuan 173 001 District Sirmour (H.P.); R.K. Patel and R.V. Singh, National Dairy Research Institute (NDRI), Karnal 132 001 (Haryana), India

We estimated and compared the energy requirements of rice and wheat crops at farmers' and improved levels of technology. Data on direct energy inputs in rice and wheat were obtained from a randomly selected sample of 191 farmers

for one agricultural year. Indirect energy inputs (which represent about 20% of the total direct energy inputs) are not accounted for in this study.

The data on per hectare energy input and output for rice and wheat at farmer's field (farmers' technology) and NDRI demonstration unit (improved technology) are presented in the table. The data suggest that farmyard manure and chemical fertilizer were the major energy inputs for rice and wheat crops under both technology levels. The use of energy from these sources was comparatively higher under the

improved technology level than under the farmers' technology level for both crops. Bullock and human labor were the next important energy inputs under farmers' technology and machinery under improved technology.

Under farmers' technology, energy use was higher for wheat; under improved technology, energy use was higher for rice. Total energy inputs, in general, were higher under farmers' technology. Nevertheless, energy output was higher with the improved than with the farmers' technology, resulting in a relatively higher energy output-input